

How MOOCS Support Collaborative and Conflict management in Schools

Fahriye Altınay

Educational Sciences Institute, Faculty of Education, Near East University Nicosia,
Northern Cyprus
Yakın Doğu Blv, Lefkoşa, Tel.: +90 392 223 64 64
fahriye.altinay@neu.edu.tr

Gokmen Dagli

Educational Sciences Institute, Faculty of Education, Near East University, Nicosia,
Northern Cyprus
Yakın Doğu Blv, Lefkoşa, Tel.: +90 392 223 64 64
University of Kyrenia, Northern Cyprus
Kyrenia Harbor, Girne, Tel.: +90 392 815 99 36
gokmen.dagli@neu.edu.tr

Zehra Altınay

Educational Sciences Institute, Faculty of Education, Near East University Nicosia,
Northern Cyprus
Yakın Doğu Blv, Lefkoşa, Tel.: +90 392 223 64 64
zehra.altinaygazi@neu.edu.tr

Abstract

Information technology plays a great role to provide the importance of sharing, exchanging knowledge for the development of people and institutions. In this respect, it is crucial to underline the significance of information technology in personal and institutional development. As information technology fosters the context of collaboration, schools have started to revamp their management practices due to these impacts. Especially, MOOCs plays a great role to improve cultural sharing, social presence as creating the manner of educational policy. In this respect, this research study evaluates the collaborative management of primary schools and their capacity in the use of information technology and MOOCs. This research study revealed that information technology fosters to use communication, interactions and exchanging knowledge in order to set mission and vision of the schools but they need to be improved through MOOCs to foster development and implementation in MOOCs.

Keywords: collaboration, information technology, management, MOOCs, transformation

1. Introduction

Information technology becomes a milestone in the education system that fosters changes and development in the education. It compromises the adoption to the global world and making lives of people closer and mutual manner. In this respect, this significant changes employ in the education that generations, their understanding, values are shaped in relation to the information technology. Therefore, information technology facilitates sharing, networking, teamwork within the construction of knowledge (Yikici, Altınay, Dagli, Altınay, 2016).

Exchanging knoweldge and experiences provides oppurtunities to upgrade the personal and institutional developments. In this respect, information technology becomes a bridge to facilitate personal and institutional developments through the changed management in schools. These developments make schools to provide qualified learning and teaching and professional development (Aksal A., 2015).

Schools become increasingly gaining cultural value in the education systems while using the merits of information technology. Management in schools acquire a adding value in the educational practice in following up contemporary trends in education (Aydn, 2014). Management becomes a collaborative and team spirit to make all activities and actions in schools for the quality. Schools

have started to implement action policy in their management by integrating the impact of information technology. In this respect, this research study aims to evaluate the role of information technology in collaborative management (Akcıl, Aksal. A., Mukhametzyanova, Gazi. A., 2016). MOOCs open a debate to set educational policy in order to develop schools to cultural sharing and digital transformation in schools. MOOCs becomes a milestone to discuss quality in education by opening up education for personal and professional development. In this respect, it is essential to consider inservice training of teachers, student satisfaction and making bridge between cross cultural contexts for the development and implementation of MOOCs. This sheds a light to empower the importance of collaboration and conflict management in order to create mutual understanding and professional mobility (Altınay, Dagli, Altınay, (2016).

The following research questions are evaluated to gain details on collaborative management and the role of the information technology.

- What are the perceptions on collaborative and conflict management in schools?
- How is the role of information technology, MOOCs in collaborative management in schools?
- How does schools set their action policy for the development?

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design

In this research an interview technique was used as a qualitative method. This technique was classified in itself as structured, semi -structured and non-structured meetings. For semi-structured meeting the questions are prepared in advance and data is collected (Karasar, 1998). This method is not as hard as structured , neither it is as flexible as non-structured meetings. It is in between the two. Because it provides the researcher with this flexibility, a semi-structured technique was used in this study.

2.2. The participants

The participants were formed through snowball sampling as an objective procedure (Tavşancıl & Aslan, 2001). Six school directors and twenty teachers from primary school in Cyprus participated in this study as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The participants

Participant	Director	Teacher	Total
School A	2	6	6
School B	2	5	7
School C	2	9	11
Total	6	20	26

2.3. Data collection process

The study took place between 28th March – 18th May with the participants at their convenience in their offices in primary schools. A 40-minute face-to-face interview was carried out to define the role of information technology to consolidate collaborative management.

2.4. Data collection tool

Questions were prepared for the participants in the above mentioned primary schools to state their views about the subject matter. The question form was examined by three experts for its content validity. Some questions were omitted because of similarity in content, some were integrated, and some questions were reconsidered for clarity. A pilot study was done with two directors and three teachers to confirm the clarity and comprehensibility of the questions as well as the relation between the questions and the given answers. The sounds recorded during the interview were then recorded on a computerised form. Two other experts were asked to examine the questions for clarity and comprehensibility, their reflection of the subject to be studied and suitability for the required information for the subject matter. There was a %91 agreement by the two experts. Following the data collection procedure, the findings were analysed content-wise in four stages.

2.5. Coding the data

A meeting document was formed after the CD recording analysis and each line was numbered. The documents and recordings were analysed by an expert for any possible incorrect or missing information. Following the completion of the meeting documents, the data was put into sections and coded. After coding and naming the data, a key list was written. The researchers, then, read each coding and numbering separately and discussed agreements/ disagreements and did necessary corrections. The reliability of the study came about as %84, which is over Miles's and Huberman's acceptable rate, %70 and over (1994). The matching codes were taken the base to reach the themes.

2.6. Setting themes

The codes set for the data were put under certain categories to form the themes. Three stages were set at this point with the directors and teachers from Demirhan, Pergama and Dörtüol primary schools to investigate the role of information technology in consolidating collaborative management system in primary education.

2.7. Arranging the data according to codes and themes

At this stage, the participants' views were explained comprehensibly and presented to the reader. Dipnoters were used to specify the participant and every utterance was put in "....." (inverted commas) as follows;

Sample 1: "....." (T. 1)

T: Teacher

D: Director

2.8. Interpretation of findings

The detailed examination, interpretation and explanation of some findings were done in this section. The collected data was interpreted through the stages required in a qualitative method some findings were explained with support from literature according to the importance of the finding.

3. Findings

Following are the perceptions of directors and teachers in primary schools in the role of information technology to enhance collaborative management system in primary education.

Dimension I: The state of collaborative and conflict management system

Views of six directors and twenty teachers were questioned about the above question and their views are presented below.

"I can say that there is a significant collaboration in every kind of activity between the director and teachers. I believe I show utmost care to provide coordination and mutual support" said D. 3. This can be assumed that the directors and teachers have set a collaborative management system and managed to make it work effectively. T. 14 disagreed saying, "As teachers we are not successful in collaborating, supporting and sharing in activities. In this respect the directors are

incompetent and ineffective. We prefer individual work more which causes a decline in the success of the school". It can be said that there are major differences between directors and teachers in respect to their views about the subject matter. Teachers admit the failure in collaborative management, support, tolerance, adaptation and coordination and prefer individual work. This can be because of the director's being ineffective in providing the requirements needed for the subject matter.

Dimension II: The effect of technology and MOOCs on communication and collaborative management system

The results and recommendations on the question above are presented in three dimensions as follows;

Dimension I: The state of collaborative management system

Six directors and 20 teachers were asked to comment on collaborative management system in primary education.

The reflection was that school directors established a collaborative management system, coordination, mutual support among teachers. However, the teachers did not approve this statement by the directors. They admitted the big difference between teachers and directors related to their views about the subject matter. They made it clear that they were not able to provide tolerance, adaptation, insight, support, and coordination among themselves, but preferred individual work.

They also pointed out the ineffectiveness of the directors and could not establish collaboration among teachers. In the light of the above statements, it is of vital importance that the subject matter is reconsidered in detail.

Dimension II: The impact between collaborative management system and communication and technology

The directors explained that they made use of all the technological facilities effectively and ran the collaborative management system successfully. However, the teachers argued the opposite and did not agree with the directors. They insisted that the directors could not put in use the technological facilities effectively, they did not have much knowledge about technology use, and they were informed very late about several activities (Schoeny, 2002)

Dimension III: Aims and Objectives in Collaborative Management System

It was found out that the directors and teachers do not share the same views about the aims and objectives in collaborative management system. They argue that they could not yet fulfill their aims and objectives. There is a strong need for a collaboration between the directors and teachers. There should be more participation in making decisions and decisions should be made together. This is the best way to fulfill aims and objectives and to achieve higher success (Aksal, A., 2015).

4. Discussion

There is an intensified need to foster merits of MOOCs to the education system in schools. Schools become a bridge to establish efficient voice of students to enhance learning. Information technology transformation force to adapt skills of new century. In this respect, MOOCs opens a gate to concentrate on open access and equality in education, especially in school context, it provides to encapsulate conflicts, leadership in different learning teaching concepts (Gazi A., Aksal A., 2017).

Digital transformation in education creates the significance of MOOCs. This makes the essence of educational policy to upgrade skills of teachers, head masters on MOOCs and information technology and use the importance of collaboration and conflict management (Akcil, Altinay, Altinay, 2016).

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